

Medimon Trading Card Game Rules

Overview and Objectives

- **Players:** 2-4 players.
 - **Life Count:** Each player starts with 25 life points.
 - **Winning Condition:** Reduce all opponents' life counts to 0. The last player standing wins the game.
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Game Setup

- **Deck requirements**
 - **Deck Size: 60**
 - **Up to 4 copies of any card**
 - **Initial Hand:**
 - Each player **draws 7** cards from their deck.
 - **Mulligan Option:** Once at the start of the game, a player may shuffle their entire initial hand back into their deck and draw a new set of 7 cards.
 - **Starting Player:**
 - Every player rolls a die. Highest number rolled goes first.
 - Turn order proceeds clockwise.
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Turn Structure

Each turn consists of four phases:

1. **Draw Phase**
2. **Play Phase**
3. **Attack Phase**
4. **Rest Phase**

1. Draw Phase

- **Action:** Draw one card from your deck.
 - **Refresh** your cards: Return all your in-play ATP cards and Medimon to their upright position to show that they are able to be used again.

2. Play Phase

- **Actions:** You may play one ATP card and any number of other cards (ie. Medimon, Treatment, Buildings) from your hand. You may also use any number of Medimon **Abilities** as long as their costs can be paid for.
 - A Medimon cannot perform an attack on the turn it is played.
 - **Exhaust:** when a card is used, it will generally become **exhausted** for the remainder of the turn. This is represented by turning the card sideways.
 - ATP cards: when exhausted, ATP cards no longer produce ATP until your next turn when they become **refreshed**.

- ATP cards become exhausted when used to pay for an ATP cost.
 - Medimon: when exhausted, Medimon can no longer attack or block until your next turn when they become refreshed.
 - Medimon become exhausted if they attack.
 - Medimon can become exhausted by certain card effects.
- **ATP Cost:** To play a card, you must pay its ATP cost by **exhausting** a corresponding number of ATP cards you control.
- **ATP Cards:**
 - ATP cards are included in your deck.
 - You may play 1 ATP card per turn and it stays in play for the remainder of the game.
 - When used to pay costs, ATP cards become **exhausted**.
- **Abilities:**
 - Many Medimon have abilities in addition to attacks. These are denoted by boxes of text without sword (attack) icons.
 - Using abilities does not inherently cause Medimon to become **exhausted**.
 - However, some abilities may cause a Medimon to become **exhausted**. This will be specified by the ability if this is the case.
 - While there are many types of abilities, they often fall into two categories: **passive abilities** and **paid abilities**.
 - **Passive Abilities:**
 - These abilities have no ATP cost associated with them.
 - Depending on the effect, these abilities may either be active at all times or will trigger at a certain time specified by the effect.
 - **Paid Abilities:**
 - These abilities have an ATP cost that must be paid in order to use them.
 - Paying the ATP cost for a paid ability causes the ability to trigger 1 time.
 - Paid abilities may be used any number of times during a player's play phase unless the ability states otherwise.
 - For example: some Medimon have paid abilities that state "this ability can be performed up to 2 times a turn."

3. Attack Phase

- **Declaring Attacks:**
 - **Select Attackers:** Choose any number of your in-play eligible Medimon to attack with. You may attack any number of opponents. A single Medimon can only attack one opponent.
 - **Declare Attacks:** Move attacking Medimon forward and announce which attacks they are using.
 - Attacks are denoted by boxes of text with sword (attack) icons.

- **Pay Attack Costs if Necessary:** Some Medimon have specific attacks that require you to pay ATP or some other cost in order to attack. All other attacks are free.
- **Attack Effects:**
 - Many attacks have effects in addition to the damage that they deal.
 - These effects trigger before opponents decide whether or not they want to block.
 - Attack effects fall into two categories: **Damage Modulators** and **Unique Effects**

- **Damage Modulators:**

- These effects directly change the amount of damage that the attack itself deals.
- These effects are represented by sword (attack) symbols with a **number and a (+) sign**.
 - These effects are often worded as “+ X damage...” where X represents a condition specified on the card.
- Example: Graves Disease's **Early Grave** attack
 - Damage for the attack is listed as “2+”.
 - The ability reads “+X damage (X = # of attacks and abilities you used this turn with reduced costs).”
 - If the attacking player had used 2 abilities with reduced costs this turn, this would translate to “This attack deals 2+2 = 4 damage this turn.”

- **Unique Effects:**

- These effects cause something to happen that is separate from the damage that the attack itself deals.
- These effects are often worded as “Also...” perform some action.
- These effects do not change the amount of damage that the attack does.
- Example: Pancreatitis' **Flare Up** attack
 - Damage for the attack is listed as “4”.
 - The effect reads “Also deal 2 damage to a player. Give that player 1 Inflammation token.”
 - If a player were to use this attack, the effect would apply to the chosen player before the defending player decides to block. Then, the defending player would choose whether or not they wanted to block the 4 damage from the attack.

- **Exhaust Attackers:** Medimon become **exhausted** after attacking.
- **Defending Against Attacks:**
 - **Defender's Choice:** The targeted opponent may choose to have their in-play Medimon block the attack(s).
 - **Blocking**
 - To block an incoming attack, the defending player puts forward one or more in-play Medimon and assigns it to an attacking Medimon.
 - A single blocking Medimon can only block one attacking Medimon.
 - Defending players may assign multiple blockers to one attacking Medimon.
 - **Battle Damage**
 - If the defending player chooses to block an incoming attack, the attacking Medimon deals damage to the blocking Medimon's health rather than to the defending player.
 - **Retaliation**
 - Blocking Medimon will always attempt to retaliate against the Medimon that is attacking.
 - If a blocking Medimon has an attack, it will use it against the attacking Medimon as if they are fighting each other.
 - All abilities of the attack apply as well.
 - If a blocking Medimon has no attack, it will not deal any damage to the attacking Medimon.
 - **Direct Damage:** If the defending player does not use Medimon to absorb the attack(s), the damage is dealt directly to their life count.
- **Inflicting Damage:**
 - **Damage Values:** Each attack has a specified damage value indicated on the Medimon card.
 - **Applying Damage to Medimon:**
 - Place damage counters on affected Medimon to track accumulated damage.
 - Damage persists across turns unless healed.
 - Damage in excess of the defender's HP does not pass through to the player unless otherwise noted.
 - **Defeated Medimon:**
 - If a Medimon's accumulated damage equals or exceeds its HP, it is discarded.

4. Rest Phase

- **Dream of Better Cards:**
 - During your rest phase, you may pay 2 ATP to draw a card. You may perform this action as many times as you wish as long as you pay the ATP cost.
- **Discarding Cards:**

- At the end of a player's turn, they must discard cards if they hold more than the maximum hand size. The maximum hand size is 7 cards. The player may choose which cards they wish to discard.

Gameplay Example

This gameplay example illustrates how a turn might proceed in Medimon, demonstrating the mechanics of playing cards, attacking, defending, and resource management.

Turn Overview: Player 1

- **Current Players:**
 - **Player 1:** Has a Hashimoto Disease Medimon in play from a previous turn.
 - **Player 2:** Has a Type II Diabetes Medimon in play.

1. Draw Phase

- **Player 1** draws one card from their deck.
- All of **player 1's** cards become **refreshed** (all are returned to their upright position so as to be used again)

2. Play Phase

- **Action:** Player 1 plays 1 ATP card (now has 3 ATP cards in play)

- Hashimoto Disease uses 2 ATP to perform the ability Sleepy (2 ATP cards are exhausted, with 1 ATP card remaining), and adds a sleep token to one of Player 3's Medimon. That Medimon now cannot perform any actions (attack/block) until the sleep token is removed (see detailed description below)

3. Attack Phase

- **Declaring Attacks:**
 - **Player 1** declares that they will be attacking Player 2 with Hashimoto Disease. Hashimoto will attack with Bull-dozer which performs $3+1=4$ damage (Player 3's Medimon with the sleep token adds +1 damage to Bull-dozer's damage)
- **Defending against attacks:**
 - **Player 2 option 1:** Block with Type II Diabetes. It will receive 4 damage from Hashimoto's Bull-dozer, which is greater than its 2 health so it will faint and be discarded. Before it faints, it will attack Hashimoto with Urinary Tract Infection for 1 damage. Hashimoto's health with now be $5-1=4$. This can be marked by adding a "1" die on Hashimoto symbolizing it has received 1 damage.
 - Hashimoto is returned to Player 1 in an exhausted state. It is not allowed to perform actions, such as block attacks from other players, until it is refreshed during Player 1's next turn.
 - Type II Diabetes is not exhausted from blocking and remains in a refreshed state.
 - **Player 2 option 2:** Not block with any Medimon and receive the damage themselves. This will decrease their life to $20-4=16$.
 - Hashimoto is returned to Player 1 in an exhausted state.

4. Rest Phase

- **Player 1** only has 1 ATP left, so cannot pay the 2 ATP to draw a card. This ends their turn.

Additional Gameplay Elements

Resource Management

- **ATP Cards:**
 - **Purpose:** Used to pay costs for playing treatments, buildings, Medimon and their abilities, and more.
 - **Drawing ATP Cards:** ATP cards are part of your deck and are drawn like any other card.
 - **Playing ATP Cards:** Only 1 ATP card can be played per turn.
 - **Using ATP Cards:**
 - In-play ATP cards can be **exhausted** (turned sideways) to use them.
 - At the beginning of your next turn, all ATP cards and Medimon are **refreshed** (returned in their upright position to show that they are available to use).
- **Building Cards / Staffing:**

- **Staff “X”:** Once during your turn, **exhaust X** Medimon you control from the family that matches the building you are staffing. The building remains staffed until the end of the turn. Draw a card when the building becomes staffed.
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Multiplayer Rules

- **Turn Order:**
 - Play proceeds clockwise from the starting player.
 - **Elimination:**
 - When a player's life count reaches 0, they are eliminated from the game.
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Rule Clarifications

- **Sequence of Phases:**
 - Complete each phase in order: Draw Phase → Play Phase → Attack Phase → Rest Phase.
 - **Retaliation Mechanics:**
 - Retaliation occurs during the Attack Phase when a defending player chooses to respond to an attack with their Medimon.
 - The defender must pay any relevant ATP costs for any retaliating attacks.
 - **Damage and Healing:**
 - Damage on Medimon remains until it is healed or the Medimon is discarded.
 - Healing effects can remove damage counters as specified by card abilities.
 - **Card Stages:**
 - Medimon cards have stages (1, 2, or 3) indicated on them.
 - The stage affects the ATP cost required to play the card.
 - **Card Abilities:**
 - Follow any special instructions or abilities written on the cards.
 - **Hand Size:**
 - The maximum hand size is 7 unless altered by an effect. If a player has more than 7 cards in their hand at the end of their turn, they must discard down to 7 at the end of their rest phase.
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Status Effects

- **Definition:**
 - Lasting effects that may be assigned to either Medimon or players.
- **Tokens:**
 - Status effects are denoted by tokens that bear the name / icon of the inflicted status.
- **Rules:**
 - Players and Medimon can each be the recipient of status effects imposed by cards within the game.

- Players and Medimon may have any number of different status effects on them.
- Players and Medimon may have any number of instances of the same status effect on them.
- Status effects persist indefinitely unless otherwise stated or until removed by some other effect.

- **Status Effect List:**

- **Inflammation:**
 - Take 1 damage at the beginning of your turn.

- **Sleep:**
 - Cannot attack, block, or pay for its abilities. If this Medimon were to refresh, remove 1 Sleep token instead.
 - Note: Passive abilities still function as normal.

- **Fatigue:**
 - Decrease damage of all attacks by 1.

- **Strengthen:**
 - Increase damage of all attacks by 1.

- **Shield:**
 - Decrease every instance of damage dealt to this Medimon by 1.

- **Fragile:**
 - Increase every instance of damage dealt to this Medimon by 1.